

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report provides the assessment of the importance of resolving air-sea interactions on meso- and sub-mesoscales for simulating tropical climate, including its major modes of sub-seasonal to seasonal variability and the West African Monsoon, as well as for simulating climate change.

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WP7

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the simulation of climate and, especially climate variability and change in the tropics by NextGEMS models. On the one hand, we have addressed the representation of mean climate and its variability in the models by comparing with observation-based products to investigate the importance of resolving air-sea interactions on km-scales for climate. On the other, we have used the simulations to explore scientific questions like projected changes in the climate system or the role of the background state in shaping teleconnections. For this two-fold purpose, we have mainly focused on multi-decadal NextGEMS simulations spanning cycles 2 to 4. We have addressed the simulation of air-sea coupled modes of variability such as the Pacific and the Atlantic Niño, their teleconnections and interactions. We have detailed the simulation of ocean upwelling regions and subtropical regions with strong presence of stratocumulus cloud decks. Finally, tropical rainfall and particularly monsoon systems have been investigated and related to the simulation of energy transports in the atmosphere and to the representation of synoptic-scale phenomena.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP7	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming (O1,O2)	yes
To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming (O1,O2)	yes
To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming. (O2)	no
To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs (O1,O2,O3)	no
To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments (O1,O2,O3)	yes
To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system (O1)	no

Synergies

This deliverable (D7.1) creates synergies with the following deliverables:

- In D7.1 we have evaluated the representation of African Easterly Waves (AEW), which impose synoptic-scale variability in West African Monsoon. These AEW are known to provide the seed for tropical cyclones in the Atlantic region. A more in depth analysis of the simulation and climate projection of such tropical cyclones is the subject of D7.2.
- D7.1 has also reported on the representation of climate, processes and teleconnections of several upwelling regions. A more in depth analysis of the impact on primary production and fisheries can be found in D7.3.
- In D7.1 we have presented analyses regarding the representation of the planetary boundary layer in regions with strong presence of stratocumulus clouds. We have also presented results where ocean mixing and the representation of the upper-most layer of the ocean is relevant. However, a more detailed analysis of developments in planetary boundary layer and ocean mixed layer schemes can be found in D7.4.

1 Overview of simulations used in this report

Table 3 provides an overview of the different experiments used throughout this report, with indication of the section in which they are analysed.

Table 3: Overview of the different km-scale simulations analysed in this report performed with ICON and IFS-FESOM models. Δx_A and Δx_O indicates the horizontal resolution of the atmosphere and ocean, respectively

Model	$\Delta x_A \times \Delta x_O$ (km)	Experiment	Period	Forcing	Section
Cycle 2					
ICON	10 × 10	ngc2013	30 yr	2020	2.2 3.4 3.5
ICON	10 × 10	rhtk001	30 yr	2020	2.2 3.4 3.5
Cycle 3					
IFS-FESOM	4.4 × 5	IFS_4.4-FESOM_5	5 yr	2020	2.4
ICON	5 × 5	ngc3028	5 yr	2020	2.4 3.1
Cycle 4					
IFS-FESOM	9 × 5	IFS_9-FESOM_5 -production	30 yr	SSP3-7.0	2.1 2.3 2.5 2.6 3.2 3.3 3.6
IFS-FESOM	9 × 5	IFS_9-FESOM_5 -production-hist	30 yr	historical	2.1 3.3
ICON	10 × 5	ngc4008	30 yr	SSP3-7.0	2.6 3.1 3.2
Other km-scale simulations					
IFS-FESOM	15 × 5 – 15	AWI-CM3-HR	10 yr	historical	3.5

2 Tropical climate, teleconnections, global warming, and climate surprises

2.1 Simulating tropical climate variability and teleconnections and their response to global warming

2.1.1 El Niño-Southern Oscillation pattern and teleconnections

The El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the leading mode of tropical interannual climate variability (Langenbrunner and Neelin, 2013). ENSO consists of alternating warm (El Niño) and cool (La Niña) anomalies in the eastern and central equatorial Pacific sea surface temperature (SST), accompanied by shifts in atmospheric pressure, winds, and convection (McGregor et al., 2022). These Pacific anomalies drive large-scale adjustments in the global atmospheric

circulation: for example, anomalous tropical convection during El Niño excites Rossby wave trains that propagate into the midlatitudes (Jiménez-Estève and Domeisen, 2020). As a result, ENSO “teleconnections” – climate anomalies remote from the tropical Pacific – emerge in many regions worldwide (e.g. North America, South Asia, Africa, and even Antarctica). ENSO’s global influence makes it the most prominent driver of year-to-year climate variability and a key source of predictability for global precipitation and climate extremes on Earth (Alizadeh, 2024). These teleconnections are most strongly expressed in precipitation and temperature anomalies.

Global climate models (GCMs) have traditionally been used to study ENSO and its teleconnections, but past-generation models (e.g., CMIP5) exhibit biases like the equatorial Pacific “cold tongue,” leading to weaker and misplaced teleconnection patterns, underrepresentation of eastern-Pacific El Niño events, and inaccurate precipitation anomalies (Bayr et al., 2024). CMIP6 models still suffer from systematic errors in simulating the tropical mean state and ENSO characteristics, impacting their teleconnection fidelity. In response, next-generation kilometre-scale models, with finer grid spacing (1–25 km), show promise in reducing these biases by explicitly resolving convection and meso-scale dynamics. Studies demonstrate that high-resolution models better capture SST and precipitation patterns, simulate ENSO-driven precipitation extremes more accurately, and reduce model uncertainty, suggesting they could significantly enhance ENSO teleconnections (Liu et al., 2022; Mahajan et al., 2023; Williams et al., 2024).

In this study, we apply kilometre-scale climate model simulations to analyze ENSO teleconnections and their changes under future warming. Specifically, we examine the global pattern of precipitation and circulation anomalies associated with ENSO during a recent historical period (1990–2019) and compare it to a mid-21st century projection (2020–2050) under anthropogenic forcing from the cycle 4 multidecadal simulations of IFS-FESOM at 9km atmosphere and 5km ocean resolution, experiments IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist and IFS_9-FESOM_5-production, respectively, in table 3. By using climate models at sufficiently high resolution, our goal is to assess whether and how these simulations could portray improvements upon past-generation biases in tropical variability and teleconnections. The scope of this work is therefore to characterise ENSO-driven precipitation and circulation anomalies in kilometre-scale models, and to compare their evolution between recent historical and future climate conditions. ICON model did not provide an historical period simulation to which compare the projection so it is not included in this analysis.

Figure 1 presents the ENSO pattern derived from observational data and from the IFS-FESOM historical simulation, based on monthly mean detrended SST anomalies. The ENSO pattern is determined through regression of the monthly detrended SST anomalies onto the detrended Niño 3.4 index. Overall, the intensity and spatial pattern of SST anomalies in the ENSO region, as well as across the global domain, exhibit a strong resemblance between the model and observed ENSO patterns. Notably, the SST signature in the tropical region (30°N to 30°S) shows remarkable agreement with the observed Hadley Centre SST pattern. However, the associated negative and positive SST anomaly patterns over the North Pacific Ocean are underestimated in the model, consistent with the associated circulation patterns, which also exhibit weaker amplitudes compared to observations (Figure 2).

We further compare the associated precipitation and circulation patterns in the reanalysis data and the IFS-FESOM historical simulation. The precipitation response shows broad similarities

Figure 1: The spatial regression of the sea surface temperature (SST) on the detrended Niño 3.4 index for the period 1990 to 2019 depicting the ENSO pattern in HadISST (left) and in IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist simulation (right) at 9km atmosphere and 5km Ocean resolution. The units are in K/K.

over the tropical oceans, though several key differences are evident. The anomalously negative precipitation anomalies over the western tropical Pacific are underestimated in the model, as are the positive precipitation anomalies over the central to eastern equatorial Pacific. This underestimation is linked to anomalous circulation patterns over the eastern equatorial Pacific, which generate a predominant easterly flow. Additionally, the north-south precipitation dipole response over eastern South Africa is captured, albeit with a reduced amplitude. The positive precipitation anomalies over the equatorial Indian Ocean are also simulated but are located further eastward in the model relative to observations, potentially associated with the spatial distribution of circulation anomalies.

Further, the positive precipitation anomalies over eastern North America and negative anomalies over northern to central Australia are reasonably well captured by the model. However, the model fails to reproduce the negative precipitation anomalies over southern Africa. Regarding circulation, while the model successfully simulates most aspects of the associated extratropical circulation patterns, the Aleutian Low response is notably weaker in the model relative to observations. Additionally, the model underestimates the high-pressure anomalies over the southeastern Pacific Ocean.

In the future scenario simulation of the IFS-FESOM, the overall precipitation response remains broadly similar to that of the historical period (Figure 3). However, the rainfall decline over the western equatorial Pacific associated with the positive phase of ENSO shows an increase in amplitude. Additionally, the positive precipitation anomalies over the equatorial Indian Ocean, southeastern North America, and South America exhibit a marked intensification. Regarding circulation, the most notable difference is the further weakening of the associated Aleutian Low.

Figure 2: The spatial regression of the total precipitation (in shading) overlaid with mean sea level pressure (MSLP, in contour) on the detrended Niño 3.4 index for the period 1990 to 2019 in GPCP/ERA5 (left) and in IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist simulation (right) at 9km atmosphere and 5km Ocean resolution. Units are in mm/day/K (hPa/K) for the shadings (contours).

2.1.2 Atlantic El Niño variability and Tropical Basin Interactions

The Atlantic basin hosts its own El Niño mode of variability, hereinafter Atlantic El Niño (AN) (Zebiak, 1993). During some periods ENSO has been found to be coupled with the Atlantic Niño mode (AN) with a lag of 6 months, an example of what is termed as Tropical Basin Interactions (TBI), which have gained relevance due to their influence on ENSO evolution (Rodríguez-Fonseca et al., 2009; Keenlyside et al., 2013). Nevertheless AN dynamics is not very well represented in current coupled models (Richter et al., 2012). In addition, due to global warming, changes in the variability climate modes are expected (Crespo et al., 2022). In this section we analyse the capability of NextGEMS IFS-FESOM model to simulate the Atlantic El Niño and its TBI and evaluate potential changes on them using the same experiments as in the previous section: the cycle 4 simulation run at 9 km in the atmosphere and 5 km in the ocean for the historical period 1990-2020 (experiment IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist in table 3), and for the mid-21st (2020-2050) century projection under the SSP3-7.0 scenario (experiment and IFS_9-FESOM_5-production in table 3). For comparison HadISST dataset (Titchner and Rayner, 2014) is employed.

In Figure 4 seasonal cycle and variability of ATL3, ATL4, NIÑO3 and NIÑO3.4 indices is shown. The model presents a warm bias in the equatorial Atlantic and a too strong seasonal cycle of mean temperature in its western part. Conversely, the seasonal cycle of the Pacific-related indices show better agreement with the observations, including the amplitude of the seasonal cycle. The model projects an increase in temperature in all indices. Regarding the interannual variability, the model overestimates its seasonal cycle not only in the Atlantic but also in the Pacific, despite the agreement on the spatial pattern shown in the previous section. In spite of that, variability peaks of the different indexes are well reproduced. The model tends to agree with the observations in the seasonal timing of the main peak of variability. Interestingly and contrary to CMIP6 projections, the model projects an increase in the ATL3 variability, while little

Figure 3: Same as in Figure 2 but from the IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation under SSP3-7.0 forcing for the period 2022 to 2049. Units are in mm/day/K (hPa/K) for the shadings (contours).

to no changes are expected for the variability in the Pacific indices.

IFS historical run simulates a strong Atlantic-Pacific connection and an even stronger projection (fig. 5), which could be related to the too strong variability detected in the Atlantic region (fig. 4). In JJA, surface wind divergence over the equatorial Pacific associated with the Atlantic is stronger in the projection compared to the historical simulation. This stronger divergence produces an extended cooling associated with a warming of the equatorial Atlantic. The different response to the Atlantic Niño on the Pacific gives rise to different extratropical teleconnections from ENSO, with strong teleconnection with eastern Europe at future scenarios with almost opposite effects over northern hemisphere at DJF (lag 6). These results put forward the possibility of Atlantic Niño being a strong source of predictability not only for ENSO but for its associated teleconnections. There is a reversal in the Northern Annular Mode (NAM) response to ENSO potentially related to a strong connection between ENSO and the Aleutians low. Also, the projection suggests a reduction of wave propagation in DJF over southern hemisphere (SH). This could be related to changes in the southern eddy driven jet, which is expected to shift poleward in response to the increase of austral summer temperatures, reducing its effectiveness as wave guide. Conversely, the SH wave propagation in JJA by the Atlantic Niño is slightly stronger in the projection.

Figure 4: Monthly SST seasonal cycle (top panels) and variability (standard deviation, bottom panels) for different oceanic indexes: a and e) ATL3, b and f) ATL4, c and g) NIÑO3, and d and h) NIÑO3.4. Blue lines correspond to HadISST, green ones to the historical simulation (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist), and reds to the future projection simulation (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production).

Figure 5: Regression maps of ATL3 SST in JJA onto anomalous SST, Z200, u10 & v10 in a) & b) lag 0 (JJA) and c) & d) lag 6 (D(0)JF(+1)). a) & c) correspond to IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist simulation and b) & d) to IFS_9-FESOM_5-production (future projection) simulation. Dots indicate regions where SST have 90% of statistical significance of the correlation, this is analogous for Z200's Solid contours. Black arrows, for its part, represent where at least 1 of the wind field component is statistically significant at 90% of confidence level.

2.2 Sensitivity of tropical climate variability to changes in the upper ocean vertical resolution

2.2.1 Tropical Basin Interactions

Long-term SST-based reanalyses reveal that teleconnections are non-stationary, varying with the ocean background state (Rodríguez-Fonseca et al., 2016). These variations stem from changes in mean state and variability, linked to decadal modes like the Atlantic Multidecadal Variability (AMV), Pacific Decadal Variability (PDV), and anthropogenic warming. Such changes reshape global atmospheric circulation and waveguides in both ocean and atmosphere. In the tropics, thermocline structure affects the propagation of oceanic Rossby and Kelvin waves, influencing heat storage and ocean-atmosphere interaction (Sprintall et al., 2020). In the atmosphere, shifts in jets like the Tropical Easterly Jet and extratropical jet streams, driven by temperature gradients, impact wave propagation and variability (Di Carlo et al., 2022). Understanding upper-ocean stratification is essential to predict modes like ENSO and the Atlantic Niño (Gévaudan et al., 2021). In this section we continue exploring the simulation of these modes of variability and their connection with an emphasis on their dependence with the representation of the upper ocean.

Accordingly, in the NextGEMS project, two simulations performed with ICON model in cycle 2 explore how varying the vertical resolution of the ocean's top 20 meters impacts climate processes. Both simulations have the same horizontal resolution (10km) and number of atmospheric levels (90). They both start from 20 January of 2020 with the same fixed forcing and run for the next 30 years. The only difference between them is found in the first 20 meters of the ocean: The reference simulation (ngc2013 in table 3) applies high-resolution physics along the 20 first meters in 10 layers, whilst the perturbed simulation (rthk001 in table 3) only consider 2 layers of 10 meters.

In this section we focus on tropical teleconnections, with a special focus on the Tropical Basin Interactions. We begin by preseting in Figure 6, the seasonal cycles for the mean and the variability at the ATL3, and NIÑO3.4 regions. Regarding the seasonal cycle of the mean, it is clear the model warm bias over the equatorial Atlantic region for both simulations, consistent with coarser grid models (Richter et al., 2012), whilst in the equatorial Pacific region, the seasonal cycle amplitude is reasonably well reproduced in the thick simulation (rthk001), being too warm in the thin one (ngc2013). Both simulations exhibit strong variability, but specially in the rthk001 for both regions. Of particular interest is the clear change in the variability for the months of June, July and August in the equatorial Atlantic Niño region. This change in the summer equatorial Atlantic variability in the simulation that only resolves the processes within the first 20 meters for 2 layers has a strong impact in TBI and in tropical- extratropical teleconnections.

The impacts and remote drivers of the boreal summer equatorial Atlantic interannual variability are analyzed in fig. 7 and 8. For the months previous to the development of the Atlantic Niño, the ngc2013 experiment (fig. 7, top-right, for MAM) presents a weakening of the South Atlantic subtropical high which conforms a cyclonic wind pattern with a weakening of the southeasterly trades and a warming of the Benguela region. In addition to this signal, there is cooling of the tropical north Atlantic (TNA) which produces trans-equatorial winds. In the JJA season, a strong

Figure 6: Monthly SST seasonal cycle (left panels) and variability (standard deviation, right panels) for different oceanic indexes: a b) Niño3.4 index, c d) ATL3 . Blue lines correspond to HadISST, black to rthk001 ICON simulation , and reds to ngc2013 ICON simulation.

convergence and a zonal SST gradient is seen in the Atlantic equatorial band. On the equatorial Pacific, strong divergence appears in the central equatorial region, together with a stronger cooling conforming a La Niña pattern, which remains in OND. This results agrees with other authors regarding the impact of the Atlantic Niño on the Pacific ENSO (Rodríguez-Fonseca et al., 2009; Polo et al., 2015; Keenlyside et al., 2013). It is in this season (OND) in which a positive NAO signal is seen in the European region, which the northern center significant, in agreement with the signature of la Niña over Europe. The impact on rainfall is, nevertheless, weak. By construction of the regression methodology, the opposite occurs for a cooling in the Atlantic (Atlantic Niña)

An interesting result emerges when analysing the low resolution simulation (rthk001), for which the stronger variability found in fig. 6 can be materialized in a stronger Atlantic Niño pattern in JJA and a stronger Pacific anomalies (fig. 8). In the months previous to the development of the Atlantic Niño (MAM), a strong la Niña pattern is already developed in the Pacific. The cold signal over the north tropical Atlantic and the weakening of the Santa Helena high pressure system is stronger than in ngc2013 (see the difference in the SLP colorbar in figs. 7 and 8). Thus, the convergence over the equatorial Atlantic is stronger, leading to the development of a stronger Atlantic Niño, which amplitudes are higher in JAS for this experiment (compare fig. 8 with fig. 7 in JJA). In addition, the stronger cooling over the TNA region could be the driver of an

EXP. NGC2013

Figure 7: Regression maps of ATL3 SST in JJA onto the anomalies of SST (units K per std deviation of index), SLP (units hPa per std of index), surface winds and rainfall (mm/day per std of the index) in left panel for ngc2013 simulations. In each panel, the regression is done onto all these variables during the previous MAM season and during the following DJF season being the lag 0 JJA. Dots indicate regions where SST have 90% of statistical significance of the correlation with JJA Atl3 index, being this significance applied for the SLP's colored contours (black for non significant regions). Winds are purple for the significant regions whilst they appear in white for the rest of the regions.

anomalous convergence over the equatorial Pacific, which triggers an anomalous downwelling oceanic kelvin wave that counteract with the Pacific Niña and helps to develop a Pacific El Niño, which signal reaches the maximum amplitude in OND (compare fig. 8 with fig. 7 in OND). This result could agree with the mechanisms proposed by Ham et al. (2014) for the TNA impact on ENSO. In addition, over Europe, the atmospheric response to El Niño resembles more an East Atlantic pattern, in agreement with Hou et al. (2023), for recent stronger El Niño events.

Overall, these simulations, although with clear biases over ATL3 and NIÑO3 mean and variability, are very promising for being used to test the role of changes in the ocean vertical resolution in the representation of the teleconnections. Our results show that a change in this resolution can affect the simulation of the global climate and particularly of ENSO predictability related to the tropical Atlantic. Further analysis (not shown) suggests that the anomalous heat content associated with both, the Atlantic and Pacific El Niños and the dynamical feedbacks associated

EXP. rTHK001

Figure 8: Same as fig. 7 but for rthk001 simulation. Notice that the amplitude of SLP colorbar is different from fig. 7.

with each of them in the rthk001 simulation are stronger than in the ngc2013 simulation.

2.2.2 The Atlantic Niño pattern

We now turn our attention to the different representation of the Atlantic Niño mode in the two simulations with upper ocean vertically thick and thick layers. The Atlantic Niño pattern has experienced changes in its amplitude and spatial configuration along the observational record coinciding with a modification of its climate teleconnections (Rodríguez-Fonseca et al., 2009; Losada et al., 2012; Losada and Rodríguez-Fonseca, 2016; Martín-Rey et al., 2018; Martín-Rey et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2024). Changes in the background state, effectiveness of its driving processes and the interaction between them have been suggested as possible causes (Martín-Rey et al., 2018; Losada et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2021; Prigent et al., 2020; Montoya-Carramolino et al., 2025).

NextGEMS simulations can help evaluate the role of the background state in the Atlantic Niño diversity. In particular, we have considered the same two twin simulations performed with ICON model during cycle 2 to explore the changes in the tropical Atlantic background state and Atlantic Niño pattern associated with different vertical ocean resolutions: ngc2013 and rthk001 in table

Figure 9: (a-d) Seasonal cycle of the zonal component of wind stress and SST (units K) along the equatorial Atlantic [3°N - 3°S] for ngc2013 (THIN layers) and rthk001 (THICK layers) simulations. (c-d) Differences of annual mean and ratio of standard deviation of SST and TAUX between rthk001 and ngc2013 simulations. Significant values exceeding 95% confidence level according to a local t-test are shown in black dots.

3, with higher and lower resolution in the upper 20 meters of the ocean, respectively. As we are mainly interested in the differences between both simulations, we will not compare with observations.

First, we analyze the ability of ICON model to simulate the seasonal cycle of equatorial Atlantic. The model exhibits a persistent westerly wind bias along the equatorial Atlantic from January to May (Figure 9a-b) that could cause the delay in the development of the cold tongue (Figure 9c-d). Notably, the equatorial cold anomalies start from the western side of the basin, contrasting with the easterly development found in observations. Notably, rthk001 (THICK layers) simulation shows a reduction of the westerly wind bias and an enhancement of the easterlies over the central-west equatorial Atlantic (Figure 9a-b). This improvement of the wind could produce the eastward shift of the cold tongue in rthk001, becoming closer to observations (Figure 9 c-d).

Regarding the changes in the background state between simulations, cooler conditions associated with enhanced zonal winds are found in rthk001 with respect to ngc2013 (THIN layers) (Fig. 9e,g), as part of an intensification of the Walker circulation over the tropical Atlantic basin that increases mean precipitation over the western boundary (not shown). rthk001 simulation also presents a general enhancement of the tropical Atlantic variability (Figure 9 f,h), consistent with the overestimation of ATL3 variability shown in the previous section.

We now focus on the Atlantic Niño pattern in JJA, which is characterized by an eastward warm tongue in June-August, driven by reduced trades over the equatorial and south Atlantic in both simulations (Figure 10 a-b). However, several differences appear between simulations. During the peak, positive SST anomalies are almost doubled in the eastern equatorial Atlantic in rthk001 with respect to ngc2013, associated with larger and more persistent wind anomalies. Cooler

Figure 10: (a-b) Regression maps of anomalous SST (K per std of index, shaded) and wind stress (vectors) in JJA over Atl3 SST index in JJA for ngc2013 (THIN layers) and rthk001 (THICK layers) simulations. Significant values are shown in black contours and vectors according to a Monte Carlo test at 90% confidence level. (c-d) Bjerknes feedback 1: Correlation maps between Atl3 SST and anomalous zonal wind in MAMJJA in ngc2013 and rthk001. (e-f) Bjerknes feedback 2: Correlation maps between Atl4 zonal wind and anomalous SSH in MAMJJA in ngc2013 and rthk001. (g-h) Bjerknes feedback 3: Correlation maps between Atl3 SSH and anomalous SST in JJA in ngc2013 and rthk001. Significant values are presented as black dots at 90% confidence level.

equatorial SST anomalies are found close to South American coast in rthk001, which disappear in ngc2013 simulation (Figure 10a-b).

A detailed analysis of the Bjerknes feedback components reveal a stronger surface-subsurface coupling in rthk001 simulation (Figure 10d,f,h). The positive SST-WIND coupling (BF1) covers the whole equatorial Atlantic basin in rthk001, while it is restricted to the western side in ngc2013 (Figure 10c-d). Maximum positive WIND-Thermocline coupling (BF2) is found in the easternmost equatorial Atlantic in rthk001 (Figure 10f), together with a stronger SST response to thermocline anomalies (BF3) (Figure 10h). In contrast, ngc2013 illustrates a westward displacement of maximum BF2 and BF3 coupling (Figure 10e,g). Our results suggest that a greater Bjerknes feedback over Atl3 region produces more intense eastward Atlantic Niño patterns, in agreement with previous studies (Montoya-Carramolino et al., 2025; Silva et al., 2021).

The reasons for the differences in tropical Atlantic mean state and variability between rthk001 and ngc2013 are still under investigation. Additional results demonstrate that rthk001 has a thicker Barrier Layer (with respect to ngc2013) that could prevent the cooling by mixing, favoring the development of more intense Atlantic Niños. Moreover, vertical mean velocity and equatorial undercurrent are enhanced in rthk001 with respect to ngc2013 (not shown), which can increase the thermocline feedback and mixing. A possible hypothesis for these changes is the enhancement of horizontal advection processes contribution in each layer in ngc2013 that could cause the weakening of the vertical ones, reducing the surface-subsurface coupling.

2.2.3 ENSO's teleconnection to Atlantic coastal upwelling system

Figure 11: Results for rthk001 (THICK layers) simulation: regression of Senegal-Mauritania (top) and NorthBenguela (center) Upwelling Indices calculated for FMA onto the previous OND SST. Regression of the DJF SST onto the NDJ Niño3.4 index (bottom)

We now turn our attention to another key feature in the Atlantic basin, the Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems (EBUS). Another application of ICON cycle 2 simulations with upper ocean vertically thin and thick layers (ngc2013 and rthk001 in table 3, respectively) is to evaluate the model performance in the simulation of the impact of ENSO in different Atlantic Upwelling regions, specifically Senegal-Mauritania (12°N-16°N, 19°W-16°W) and Northern Benguela (29°S-15°S; 10°E-18°E). To characterize the upwelling in the two regions, we use as an index the area-averaged meridional component of the wind stress in each box for the February to April season (FMA).

rthk001 simulation captures correctly the observed relationship between ENSO and Senegal-Mauritania and Northern Benguela upwelling systems: La Niña conditions in the Pacific enhance upwelling in Senegal Mauritania (Wade et al., 2023, Figure 11, top), while El Niño conditions in the Pacific enhance upwelling in Northern Benguela (Rouault and Tomety, 2022, Figure 12, center). Conversely, ngc2013 simulation does not show a relation between Atlantic EBUS and ENSO (Figure 12, top, center). The variability in this simulation seems to be related to local processes, with very weak regression values elsewhere.

To evaluate potential causes for this discrepancy between the simulated impacts of ENSO on Atlantic EBUS, we calculate the regression of the global SST and z200 onto the Winter (NDJ) Niño3.4 index (Fig. 11). The regressions show that ngc2013 simulates a more Central Pacific Niño, triggering an atmospheric wave located to the west in comparison with rthk001. Such

Figure 12: Results for ngc20013 (THIN layers) simulation: regression of Senegal-Mauritania (top) and NorthBenguela (center) Upwelling Indices calculated for FMA onto the previous OND SST. Regression of the DJF SST onto the NDJ Niño3.4 index (bottom)

westward shift produces an Atlantic response to the west from the African coast, and reduces the impact of ENSO on the Atlantic EBUS.

2.3 Seasonality of upwelling in tropical Angolan upwelling system

2.3.1 Motivation and setting

The tropical Angolan upwelling system (tAUS) at the eastern boundary of the South Atlantic extends from the Angola-Benguela frontal zone at about 17°S to the mouth of the Congo River at 6°S . In contrast to the poleward northern Benguela upwelling region, upwelling and productivity in the tAUS follow a clear seasonal cycle, as productivity peaks in austral winter in a narrow strip along the Angolan coast (Brandt et al., 2023). However, the maximum in productivity in the tAUS is not controlled by local wind-driven upwelling. Instead, seasonal upwelling variability is remotely forced and closely connected to equatorial dynamics. Zonal wind fluctuations at the equator excite equatorial Kelvin waves, which propagate eastward, and upon encountering the eastern boundary, part of their energy is transformed into poleward propagating coastal trapped waves (CTWs) causing the seasonal upwelling signal in the tAUS (Körner et al., 2024).

In this section we evaluate whether the nextGEMS production run from IFS-FESOM model can resolve these processes and thus may be used to predict upwelling variability in the future. Output of the cycle 4 IFS-FESOM production run (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production in table 3) is compared to long-term hydrographic observations (RV Nansen cruises 1995 to 2014 (Tchipalanga

et al., 2018)), BANINO and other cruises to the region) and satellite altimetry.

Figure 13: Panel a) shows region (red) of averaged observations and model data in b). Panel b) shows zonal SST variability in the tropical Angolan upwelling region from the coast to 120 km offshore for February through April (FMA) and July through September (JAS) calculated from observations (OBS, black lines) and the IFS_9-FESOM_5-production run (blue lines). Numbers indicate coastal (5km) to offshore (120km) temperature difference. Dashed lines show offshore SST for reference. Region of averaged observations and model data is indicated by the red area in the left panel.

Due to two observed favorable properties, (i) statistically insignificant long-term trend in surface properties, and (ii) latitudinal constancy of surface properties, we chose the band between the Congo river mouth at 6.3°S and Benguela at 12.6°S for validation region (Fig. 13a). This way, only coast distance and season remain as significant influencing variables, so that averages can be taken over latitude and essentially two decades of time.

2.3.2 Model performance

Beginning with sea surface temperature (SST), the model starts too warm and shows a strong increasing trend of almost 1 K per decade, and additionally shows a latitudinal gradient in the Congo-Benguela band. Even if both findings contradict the observations, we still adhere to the averaging over latitude and time for reasons of comparability, though keeping the discrepancies in mind. When now comparing the longitudinal SST profiles during maximum SST in February to April (FMA), and during minimum SST in July to September (JAS, winter upwelling), we find most striking that the winter SST drop near the coast is much too weak (Fig. 13b).

Sea level anomaly (SLA) is investigated to evaluate the presence and properties of the seasonal CTW in the model. This gives an indication of the presence and phase of CTWs, although no information on the inner density structure, i.e. on higher modes. In the Hovmoeller diagram we find strong similarity of model and satellite observations (Fig. 14), in seasonality, amplitude, and propagation velocity along the coast. Only a very fast positive structure in April/May finds no equivalent in observations, which is probably remotely forced by unrealistic changes in the equatorial wind field.

Figure 14: Average sea level anomaly in millimeters along the eastern boundary of the African coast from the equator to 25°S from IFS-FESOM (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation, panel a) and satellite altimetry (panel b) taken from Rouault (2012).

For the CTWs to significantly impact the near surface variability and thus upwelling in the tAUS region, they need to interact with the sloping eastern boundary topography and thereby scatter energy into higher baroclinic modes (Körner et al., 2024). The comparison of the ocean density structure along the continental slope (Fig. 15) is focused at around 11°S and done as difference plot between the two time periods February through April and July through September to allow a direct comparison with observations (Körner et al., 2024). The results suggest similarities in the structure of the density changes between the model and observations, namely a raising of the isopycnals above about 300m, and a lowering of the isopycnals below about 300m. Additionally, the density displacements increase towards the coast (Fig. 15) in both model and observations, although the features are weaker in the model than in the observations. Nonetheless, the model is principally able to correctly represent seasonality and baroclinic structure of the passing higher-modal CTW - which requires the CTWs to interact with the high-resolution topography present in the kilometer-scale run.

Figure 15: Difference plots of density structure between July-September (JAS) and February-April (FMA) seasons, for a) IFS-FESOM (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation) and b) observations (Körner et al., 2024). Red colors indicate isopycnals displaced towards the surface, while blue colors indicate isopycnals displaced to greater depth. Please note differences in color scale in a) and b).

Another potential cause for the too weak cooling of coastal waters during winter upwelling could be an under-representation in the model of the vertical mixing caused by baroclinic tides, which was found to be responsible for the coastal cooling when CTWs are present (Körner et al., 2023). However, mixed layer depth (MLD) distributions in model and observations (Fig. 16) suggest similar MLDs near the coast in the seasonal course. Similarly, the vertical temperature gradient and the stratification N^2 below the mixed layer were found to closely agree with observations, with differences smaller than 20%. Offshore, however, the MLD is found to be too shallow (about factor 0.6 of observed MLD values), which might provide an explanation to a possible low vertical mixing despite the realistic MLD and vertical temperature gradients at the coast.

Figure 16: Depth of mixed layer (MLD) in a) FESOM (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation) and b) observations within 20 km off the coast. MLD was calculated as the depth where surface density increased by 0.15 kg m^{-3} to avoid sensitivity to diurnal warm layers.

In summary, the comparison between the cycle 4 IFS-FESOM production run and observations reveals substantial similarities in the spatial and temporal hydrographic patterns and physical processes, some of which require elevated horizontal resolution such as CTW - topography interaction. However, an unrealistic background state having too high sea surface temperatures in this region remains. Furthermore, sea surface temperatures warm by about 1 K per decade in the simulation in the years from 2020 to 2050, while observations suggest a warming of only 0.2 K per decade in the last 20 years (Sweijd and Smit, 2020).

2.4 Mesoscale variability of stratocumulus in storm resolving models

2.4.1 Introduction

In a recent study, the representation of the global climatology of low-level clouds by km-scale models was described (Nowak et al., 2025). The models properly captured the annual cycle of stratocumulus albedo and its relationship with environmental parameters. However, the nextGEMS models, ICON and IFS, exhibited large albedo differences among them, particularly

over coastal regions. Since these models employed unprecedentedly high-resolution grids for extended simulation periods, and the study relied on space-time averages, it raised questions about their ability to represent shorter temporal (diurnal) and spatial (mesoscale) variability.

Stratocumulus clouds are influenced by environmental factors that differ across offshore, coastal, and land regions. Offshore conditions feature weaker subsidence and stability, and warmer sea surface temperatures, favoring deeper boundary layers. Coastal zones, in particular, have a sharp land-sea contrast of momentum, mass, and energy, which induces mesoscale systems such as land-sea breezes and coastal low-level jets.

In the present study, we use global km-scale models to investigate how they represent the stratocumulus-topped boundary layers and their modulation across offshore, coastal, and land environments. The models offer an opportunity to contrast the minimal set of parameterizations in ICON with IFS, which employs complex parameterizations, including eddy-diffusivity mass-flux and convection schemes.

2.4.2 Material and Methods

The simulations analyzed were performed with two global km-scale Earth system models: the ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic (ICON) model (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) model coupled to the Finite-volume Sea ice-Ocean Model (FESOM) (Rackow et al., 2025). Simulations from the third cycle of the nextGEMS (ngc3028 and IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 in table 3) were used since they were performed with high resolution (4 - 5 km) and ran for five years (Segura et al., 2025).

The nextGEMS models are described in detail in Hohenegger et al. (2023) and Rackow et al. (2025), and the main characteristics of the simulations related to the present work are described in Table 4. Although IFS simulations have 137 vertical levels (Table 4), only 23 levels are saved as the output. Considering the 137 vertical levels in the IFS, there are 31 levels below 3 km.

Table 4: Characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations. The columns show (from left to right) the nextGEMS development cycle, simulation short name, atmospheric model, approximate horizontal grid spacing (Δx), number of vertical levels, number of vertical levels below 3 km height, turbulence model, use of the deep convection, and shallow convection schemes.

Cycle	Simulation	Model	Δx	# _{lev}	# _{lev} <3 km	Turbulence scheme	Deep convec.	Shallow convec.
3	ngc3028	ICON	5 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
3	IFS_4.4 -FESOM_5	IFS	4 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on "1/5"	on

*Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux

The analysis was performed for August, the month with the highest top-of-atmosphere (TOA) albedo (Nowak et al., 2025). Building on the offshore regions analyzed by Nowak et al. (2025),

namely the Californian, Peruvian and Namibian regions, we focused on their central latitudes, extended the analysis inland toward the upwind land surface, and looked into the diurnal cycle.

2.4.3 Results and Discussion

The models' vertical-longitudinal cross-sections of wind (Fig. 17) and cloud liquid water content (Fig. 18) are shown for the three analyzed regions and at different times of the day to capture both the diurnal cycle and regional characteristics. The first row in these figures corresponds to the time closest to sunrise. Qualitatively, both models represent the diurnal and longitudinal boundary layer variability.

Figure 17: Vertical-longitudinal cross-sections of wind represented by the IFS (IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 simulation, left) and ICON (ngc3028 simulation, right) models, averaged over August. The meridional component is shaded, while arrows represent the zonal and vertical components. The land surface is shown in brown.

The simulations represented the atmospheric systems that modulate the wind regime of each stratocumulus area (Fig. 17). In the coastal region, the wind shows a more pronounced diurnal cycle. This variability is associated with the land-sea thermal contrast that induces the mesoscale land-sea breeze. For instance, when the overland air temperature is warmer (not shown), westerly onshore winds intensify in Californian at 16 local time and Namibian between 13 and 19 local time. On the synoptic scale, semipermanent subtropical high-pressure systems are the main wind drivers (Ranjha et al., 2013). These systems drive northeasterly winds in the Californian region and southeasterly winds in the Peruvian and Namibian regions (Fig. 17). In all regions, there is a core with stronger boundary layer winds, which are stronger and closer to the coast in the southern hemisphere regions (Fig. 17). This wind core is associated with the coastal low-level jet occurrence, a typical mesoscale phenomenon observed along the western shores of continents in the subtropical areas (Lima et al., 2018; Ranjha et al., 2013). They usually have positive feedback with the coastal upwelling in the ocean, which in turn is linked to the presence of stratocumulus clouds.

A remarkable characteristic of the stratocumulus cloud profile is that its base lowers toward the coast (Fig. 18). According to previous studies, increased sea surface temperatures as one moves away from the coast and towards the equator induce the boundary layer to deepen and surface latent heat fluxes to increase, favoring the transition from stratocumulus to cumulus

Figure 18: Same as Figure 17, but for cloud liquid water content.

(e.g., Bretherton and Wyant, 1997; Sandu and Stevens, 2011).

The clouds also presented a diurnal modulation (Fig. 18), with cloud liquid water content maximum at night and minimum in the early afternoon (Fig. 18). Stratocumulus clouds have diurnal modulation, mainly driven by the daily cycle of solar insolation (Wood, 2012). During the daytime, increased solar radiation absorption in the upper regions of the cloud weakens the total radiative driving. This leads to weaker circulations (Hignett, 1991) and less efficient coupling of the clouds and the surface moisture supply (Bretherton et al., 2004).

However, there are also differences between the model results due to the use of distinct parameterizations. ICON has a shallower cloud base and larger cloud liquid water content than IFS and observations (Nowak et al., 2025). This is possibly due to lower inversion heights, near-surface temperatures, and insufficient mixing between the boundary layer and the free troposphere due to its local turbulence scheme (Nowak et al., 2025). In contrast, with its non-local turbulence model and cloud-top entrainment component (Köhler et al., 2011), IFS better represents the cloud liquid water content and cloud base height (Nowak et al., 2025).

In summary, this study examined how ICON and IFS-FESOM global models using km-scale horizontal grids represent subtropical stratocumulus-topped boundary layer regimes and their modulation across offshore, coastal, and land environments, as well as the diurnal cycle. Both models appropriately represented the synoptic-scale flow driven by subtropical anticyclones and the mesoscale coastal land-sea breeze and low-level jets. The models also agree on the vertical structure with shallow clouds below 3 km, whose base lowers toward the coast, and the maximum cloud liquid water content at night. The striking difference between the models was that ICON represented a shallower cloud base and larger cloud liquid water content than IFS and observations. This difference may be attributed to subgrid mixing representation and environmental factors discussed in more detail in Nowak et al. (2025). We are currently quantifying the environmental factors that influence stratocumulus clouds over offshore and coastal environments to infer whether these factors or the representation of subgrid processes in the model are responsible for the albedo bias. We are also analyzing horizontal cross-sections to better characterize the model representation of stratocumulus mesoscale organization.

2.5 Precipitation and its impacts on Pacific warm pool extension

Precipitation influences upper ocean salinity and temperature across a wide range of temporal and spatial scales. In this section, we examine the coupling between precipitation, surface winds, and upper ocean variables such as mixed layer depth, salinity, and sea surface temperature (SST). For the analysis, we select an El Niño year (2024) and a La Niña year (2028) from the cycle 4 production run from the IFS-FESOM model (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation in table 3).

Figure 19: Time–longitude sections of key variables averaged over the equatorial zone (5°S–5°N, 120°E–270°E) during an El Niño year (2024; panels a–f) and a La Niña year (2028; panels g–l) in IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation. (a, g) Niño 3.4 index; (b, h) daily precipitation (Tp, mm); (c, i) daily mean 10-m zonal wind (U10, $m \cdot s^{-1}$); (d, j) daily mean sea surface temperature anomaly (SST, °C); (e, k) daily mixed layer depth anomaly (MLD, m); (f, l) daily mean surface salinity anomaly (SOS, $g \cdot kg^{-1}$). Black contours indicate the position of the equatorial warm pool, SST equals 28.5°C.

During the El Niño year, warmer waters extending eastward into the Niño 3.4 region reduce the large-scale zonal SST gradient (Figure 19 d) by early March 2024. This weakened gradient creates favorable conditions for the development of El Niño. As shown in Figure 19 b and c,

frequent precipitation and westerly wind events (WWEs) occur from April 2024 onward, consistent with the eastward expansion of the warm pool region (outlined by black contours in Figure 19). In response to the frequent precipitation in the western Pacific, surface salinity is significantly reduced (Figure 19 f), which stabilizes the water column and suppresses vertical mixing. Consequently, the mixed layer depth becomes shallower (Figure 19 e), further enhancing sea surface warming.

Due to the cold SST anomaly during the La Niña year, precipitation in the western Pacific (Figure 19 h) is less frequent than during the El Niño year. The easterly surface winds along the equator (Figure 19 i) are significantly stronger than those observed during the El Niño year, which suppresses the occurrence of westerly wind events. Additionally, the eastern edge of the warm pool region is confined west of 225°E. As a result of reduced precipitation and enhanced evaporation induced by the strengthened easterly trade winds, surface salinity anomalies are particularly high in the western equatorial Pacific (Figure 19 l). The mixed layer depth is deepened (Figure 19 k) due to enhanced vertical mixing driven by strong easterly winds and the increased density of saltier surface waters. As a feedback, a deeper mixed layer is often associated with cooler SST, as stronger vertical mixing spreads surface heat downward and brings colder subsurface water to the surface.

To understand the feedback processes between SST and other variables shown in Figure 19, daily SST and SST anomalies (SSTa), along with their relationships to each variable at each grid point within the equatorial region (5°N–5°S, 120°E–270°E), are presented as scatter density plots in Figure 20. In the El Niño year, westerly wind events (WWEs) occur more frequently when SST exceeds 30 °C (Figure 20 El Niño (a)), consistent with Fig. 19c, which shows WWEs primarily occurring in the western Pacific warm pool. Interestingly, strong easterly winds also coincide with warm SST anomalies (Figure 20 El Niño (e)), possibly due to reduced precipitation and enhanced solar radiation during these periods, which together support surface warming.

Precipitation increases with SST, peaking near 31 °C (Figure 20 El Niño (b)). However, maximum precipitation is often followed by a cold SST anomaly (Figure 20 El Niño (f)), likely due to reduced solar heating and the formation of a stable freshwater lens that inhibits vertical mixing of warm subsurface water.

Mixed layer depth (MLD) shows a nonlinear relationship with SST. It shallows as SST rises above 28°C, reaching a minimum around 31°C. This coincides with peak precipitation (Figure 20 El Niño (b)) and minimum surface salinity (Fig. 20 El Niño (d)), suggesting precipitation-driven freshwater input influences MLD. This relationship is further supported by Figure 20 El Niño (g), where positive SST anomalies correspond to negative MLD anomalies—indicating a shallower mixed layer during warmer SST periods. When SST is below 28°C, MLD deepens with increasing SST, reaching its maximum around 28°C where surface easterlies also peak (Figure 20 El Niño (a)).

In the La Niña year, WWEs are less frequent overall but still increase in occurrence when SST exceeds 31°C (Figure 20 La Niña (a)). Unlike in El Niño, strong surface easterlies during La Niña are consistently associated with cold SST anomalies (Figure 20 La Niña (e)), likely due to greater SST sensitivity to wind-induced latent heat flux and enhanced surface cooling.

Precipitation during La Niña also increases with SST (Figure 20 La Niña (b)), with maximum

rainfall again aligning with cold SST anomalies (Figure 20 La Niña (f)), similar to the El Niño case. The MLD–SST relationship during La Niña is similar in pattern but shifted toward colder conditions. As shown in Figure 20 La Niña (g), deeper MLD anomalies (MLDa) are associated with colder SST anomalies (SSTa), reaching their greatest depth when SSTa is approximately -2°C . This aligns with the strongest surface easterly winds, which also peak at similar SSTa values.

Therefore, El Niño and La Niña exhibit distinct SST–atmosphere feedbacks along the equator. During El Niño, WWEs are more frequent and associated with high SSTs, while strong easterlies can still align with warm SST anomalies due to reduced cloud cover and increased solar input. In contrast, La Niña features fewer WWEs, and strong easterlies consistently correspond to cold SST anomalies, reflecting higher SST sensitivity to wind-induced surface cooling. MLD deepens with wind strength and SST in both years but reaches its maximum under colder SST conditions during La Niña, highlighting more vigorous wind-driven mixing in cooler states.

Figure 20: Scatter density plots for an El Niño year (top row) and a La Niña year (bottom row), showing the relationships between various variables and (a–d) sea surface temperature (SST), and (e–h) SST anomalies (SSTa), defined relative to the multi-year daily mean over 2020–2049 in IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation. The variables include: (a, e) 10 m zonal wind, (b, f) daily precipitation, (c, g) mixed layer depth and its anomaly, (d, h) surface salinity and its anomaly. All data are from the equatorial region ($5^{\circ}N$ – $5^{\circ}S$, $120^{\circ}E$ – $270^{\circ}E$).

2.6 ITCZ Biases and Energy transports

Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) biases and their relation to the atmospheric energy budget were investigated yet in the report of Deliverable 6.1 (RD6.1). We here present an extension of the analysis of symmetric and asymmetric tropical precipitation biases, and both include and focus on the nextGEMS cycle 4 simulations (C4-kGCMs), namely the IFS-FESOM (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production in table 3) and ICON (ngc4008 in table 3) production runs. These consist in projection runs following SSP3-7.0 scenario starting from 2020 and run with a resolution of 9 km in the atmosphere and 5 km in the ocean for IFS_9-FESOM_5-production and 10 km in the atmosphere and 5 km in the ocean for ICON ngc4008.

In Figure 21 we present the precipitation climatology of C4-kGCMs along with the observational dataset GPCP as well as the models' biases relative to GPCP. We first note that C4-kGCMs simulate the principle circulations of the tropical atmosphere and their precipitation patterns: monsoon systems, the Hadley circulation and the Intertropical Convergence Zone. Still, tropical precipitation is systematically overestimated with respect to GPCP observations: the tropical mean of precipitation (GPCP: $P=3.03\text{mm day}^{-1}$) is overestimated in C4-k-GCMs: ICON ngc4008 gives 3.94 and IFS_9-FESOM_5-production 3.62 mm day^{-1} .

Figure 21: C4-kGCMs temporal mean of the precipitation flux (panels a,c) and biases with respect to observations GPCP [mm day^{-1}] (panel b,d). In panel e) the zonal mean is shown and in panel f) GPCP observations for the period 1979-2014. For the models (C4_ICON_10-5 for ICON ngc4008 simulation and C4_FIFS_9-5 for IFS_9-FESOM_5-production) the complete simulated periods were used. The tropical mean of precipitation flux (within 30°S and 30°N) is noted as \bar{P}^{trop} and the root mean square error of precipitation flux is noted as \overline{RMSE}^{trop} .

In Figure 21e we also present the zonal mean of the climatology of precipitation, which demonstrate both the dryness along the Equator in C4-kGCMs as well as the overestimation of both southern and northern hemispheric ITCZ rainbands. Further, the latitudes of maximum precipitation, that represent the location of the ITCZ south and north of the Equator, are found shifted polewards. The structure of the ITCZ in the Pacific, as revealed by GPCP observations, is characterized by a sharp and intense northern branch and a southwards slanting southern branch,

Figure 22: Interhemispheric Asymmetry (IHA) of atmospheric energy balance terms and precipitation flux (pr) integrated globally ($[0^\circ; 90^\circ]$). Observations for R_{TOA} (CERES) and pr (GPCP) are shown with black markers. For the models blue (C4_ICON_10-5 for ICON ngc4008 simulation) and orange (C4_FIFS_9-5 for IFS_9-FESOM_5-production) is used.

resulting in a structure referred to as a double ITCZ. In all generations of climate models the prominent double ITCZ bias can be identified by the underestimation of precipitation along the Equator (Tian and Dong, 2020), as well as by the overestimation of the southern and northern branch of the ITCZ. In particular ngc4008 is very dry along the Equator in the Pacific. This goes along with low surface winds, suggesting that schemes of surface fluxes need to be adjusted (not shown). In IFS_9-FESOM_5-production the southward slanting of the ITCZ in the southern Pacific is underestimated. The structure of the ITCZ, whether single-branched and symmetric across the Equator or double-branched, can be characterized by the equatorial precipitation index E_P :

$$E_P = \frac{[P]_{2^\circ S - 2^\circ N}}{[P]_{20^\circ S - 20^\circ N}} - 1. \quad (1)$$

where $[P]_{\phi_1 - \phi_2}$ is the zonal mean precipitation averaged between latitudes ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . For GPCP observations E_P is 0.13. For C4-k-GCMs it becomes negative, demonstrating the lack of precipitation close to the Equator. Consequently E_P suggests that the double ITCZ-problem is not mitigated but instead amplified in nextGEMS C4-kGCMs.

In Figure 22 we present the inter-hemispheric asymmetry (IHA) of the atmospheric energy balance terms and precipitation flux, defined as:

$$IHA(\times) = \times|_{\phi>0} - \times|_{\phi<0}. \quad (2)$$

where \times can be the net energy input (NEI), or any of its constituents. Here the net energy input results from net top-of-atmosphere radiative fluxes (R_{TOA}) and the net combined surface fluxes (RF_{SFC}) that comprise surface turbulent enthalpy fluxes (F_{SFC}) and surface radiative fluxes (R_{SFC}), all components taken as positive if entering the atmospheric column. We first

note that in ERA5 precipitation IHA is globally ($[0^\circ; 90^\circ]$) NH heavy, whereas it is SH heavy in C4-kGCMs. Likewise the IHA of NEI is globally NH-heavy, for both ERA5 and C4-kGCMs. But C4-kGCMs underestimate this asymmetry and consequently we find that both the NEI and precipitation are displaced southwards. Further we find that R_{TOA} is globally SH-heavy, with IFS_9-FESOM_5-production over-estimating this asymmetry and ICON ngc4008 being hardly biased. Instead, combined surface fluxes (RF_{SFC}), are globally NH-heavy, with ICON ngc4008 underestimating this asymmetry and IFS_9-FESOM_5-production being hardly biased. It is here that C4-kGCMs differ, with biases in the IHA of NEI stemming from R_{SFC} in ICON ngc4008, and from R_{TOA} for IFS_9-FESOM_5-production. Instead the SH-heavy IHA of F_{SFC} is weakly biased. Consequently for ICON 4008 biases in the IHA of RF_{SFC} stem from R_{SFC} . The IHA of R_{SFC} is NH-heavy and here ICON ngc4008 underestimates this asymmetry, while IFS_9-FESOM_5-production is hardly biased.

In summary we report that both symmetrical and asymmetrical tropical precipitation biases, representative of ITCZ biases, are unmitigated in C4-kGCMs. The symmetrical precipitation index E_P is found negative in C4-kGCMs, different to GPCP observations, and demonstrates both dryness along the Equator and overestimated northern and southern ITCZ branches, meaning that the long standing ITCZ problem in climate models also persists in C4-kGCMs. An analysis of the interhemispheric asymmetry of precipitation and the atmospheric energy balance terms demonstrates that C4-kGCMs are too symmetrical across the Equator, in both precipitation and net energy input. We find that these biases result from biased asymmetries in surface radiative fluxes in ICON ngc4008 and in top-of-atmosphere radiative fluxes in IFS_9-FESOM_5-production. Instead, the interhemispheric asymmetry of surface turbulent enthalpy fluxes is well-estimated in C4-kGCMs relative to ERA5 reanalyses.

3 Monsoon variability, extreme rainfall, and climate change

3.1 Moist energetics of global monsoons

We summarize monsoon precipitation biases in the boreal summer and winter seasons for ICON cycles 3 and 4 (simulations ngc3028 and ngc4008 in table 3, respectively), along with the associated low level wind vectors (Fig. 23). Two key biases are obvious in these maps. The first, which is consistent across cycle 3 and 4, is the lack of precipitation along the equator and the double inter tropical convergence zone (ITCZ), which was highlighted in the previous section. Instead, an aspect of the tropical precipitation that appears to have deteriorated between cycle 3 and cycle 4 concerns the monsoon systems, which in cycle 4 reach much further into the continents than GPCP observations show, with this bias particularly notable in the West African and Australian monsoons. Also worth of notice are excessive precipitation in the southern Indian Ocean both during JJA and DJF, and a very dry Arabian Sea in JJA.

Sources of possible precipitation biases have previously been interpreted through the lenses of a 2D atmospheric energy budget framework (Boos and Korty, 2016). The associated arguments rest on the idea that the divergent (irrotational) component of time-mean wind, which produces nearly all tropical rainfall, is closely associated with the divergent component of tropical atmo-

Figure 23: ICON cycles 3 and 4 precipitation (mm/day) and near-surface winds against GPCP precipitation and ERA5 near-surface winds for JJA (left) and DJF (right).

spheric energy transport $\langle \vec{u}h \rangle$ (with moist static energy h), in turn constrained to satisfy energy balance:

$$\frac{\partial \langle \mathcal{E} \rangle}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \langle \vec{u}h \rangle = NEI = R_{TOA} - F_{sfc}, \quad (3)$$

with \mathcal{E} the storage term, \vec{u} the horizontal wind, NEI the net energy input into the atmospheric column, R_{TOA} TOA radiative fluxed and F_{sfc} surface fluxes. On seasonal means, when the storage term is small, an energy flux potential χ can then be defined such that

$$\nabla^2 \chi = NEI, \quad (4)$$

and whose gradient is the divergent component of the atmospheric energy transport:

$$\nabla \chi = (uh, vh). \quad (5)$$

Ascending branches of time-mean meridional overturnings are expected to lie near latitudes where both $\langle vh \rangle = 0$ and $\partial_y \langle vh \rangle > 0$ (the energetic flux equator, EFE), while ascent in time-mean tropical zonal overturning is expected to lie near longitudes where $\langle uh \rangle = 0$ and $\partial_x \langle uh \rangle > 0$, defined as energy flux prime meridians (EFPM).

As expected, both in ngc4008 and ERA5, regions of maximal precipitation coincide with minima in the energy flux potential (maximum energy flux divergence, see Figs. 24 and 25). Heavy rainfall generally occurs near the EFE, but is enhanced near an EFPM. Given that precipitation biases in ICON cannot simply be explained as meridional shifts, but have a complex zonal structure, it is not straightforward to relate energetic metrics, such as the EFE, to such precipitation biases, as done in previous studies, and more work is required. However, it is interesting to notice some consistent behaviours, such a westward bias of the EFPM during DJF in ICON relative to ERA5, consistent with more pronounced rainfall over the Indian ocean and the Australian continent.

Figure 24: NH summer (JJA) precipitation and energy-based metrics: precipitation (shading), χ (red contours, interval 0.1 PW, with equatorial extrema being minima), the divergent vertically integrated atmospheric energy flux (vectors), and zero lines of the meridional and zonal divergent energy flux (the EFE, orange line and EFPM cyan line) for ngc4008 (top) and ERA5(bottom).

Biases in precipitation and χ are more explicitly shown in Fig. 26 (top row), where regions of enhanced energy divergence in ICON relative to ERA5 (negative bias in χ) are broadly consistent with excessive precipitation. We particularly note the pronounced and elongated region of χ bias during SH summer.

One of the advantages of the energetic framework is that, thanks to its linearity, it allows us to quantify how biases in individual components of the *NEI* contribute to the total χ bias. We find that the largest contribution, both in terms of magnitude and spatial pattern especially for SH summer, comes from biases in surface LH flux (Fig. 26, bottom row).

Biases in LH fluxes (not shown) feature strong positive biases at the monsoon fringes where the ICON model in cycle 4 exaggerates the progression. These biases confirm that the strong pole in the LH potential (Fig. 26) is associated mainly with errors over land, and receives contributions from Southern Africa, the maritime continent as well as across Australia.

Figure 25: Same as Fig. 24 but for SH summer (DJF).

Figure 26: Total biases in energy flux potential χ (ngc4008 – ERA5, PW) (top) and contribution from LH flux biases (bottom) for NH (left) and SH (right) summer

3.2 Analysis of the moist static energy budget in the western African monsoon region

Expanding on the global analyses presented in the previous section, here we investigate the representation of the West-African Monsoon (WAM) in the 30-year nextGEMS cycle 4 (C4) simulations with ICON (ICON4, simulation ngc4008 in table 3) and FESOM-IFS (FIFS4, simulation IFS_9-FESOM_5-production in table 3). Specifically, we present the models' biases with respect to observations and their near-term climate change trend and interpret both through the lenses of the moist static energy (MSE) budget (see Eq. 6). For the specific case of the WAM, the MSE budget has provided fundamental insights into the role that the proximal Saharan desert plays in both limiting its poleward extent and in regulating its year-to-year variability through ventilation of mid-level low MSE air (Chou and Neelin, 2003; Shekhar and Boos, 2017).

The climate change response of the WAM in many generations of climate model inter-comparisons has been found strongly diverging, both in terms of magnitude and sign of the precipitation response (Held et al., 2005). In this regard, the hypothesis that the Saharan shallow meridional circulation might inhibit the WAM convection provides an explanation behind this large spread across models: Hill et al. (2017) showed how two different convective parameterizations in the same GCM yield very different responses to uniform SST warming driven by different shallow Saharan flows. It is therefore of interest to revisit this question in the context of the two km-scale NextGEMS models, in which deep convection is either not parameterized (ICON4) or parameterized with a model physics that mimics behaviour at km-scale, due to a substantially reduced (factor 6) cloud base mass flux in the deep convection scheme (FIFS4).

Figure 27a-b shows the July-to-September (JAS) WAM precipitation climatology for the first ten simulated years 2020-2029, along with observations (GPCP for years 1979-2014, panel g) and respective biases (panels c-d). FIFS4 realistically represents WAM precipitation, with the only substantial biases being found along the western coastline and a southward-shifted Atlantic ITCZ. As discussed in the previous section, ICON4 produces an overly intense WAM that extends into the southern Saharan desert.

Moving to the question of the projected response in the two models, Figure 27e-f shows the climate change trend, computed by subtracting the JAS precipitation averaged over the first ten simulated years (2020-2029) from that averaged over the last ten simulated years (2040-2049). In ICON4, the trend indicates an intensification and northward expansion of the monsoonal rainfall. Instead, in FIFS4 the trend in WAM precipitation over the Sahel region is weak and not robust. Only off the west coast of Africa and within the Gulf of Guinea a clear precipitation trend is found, with a southward rainfall shift in FIFS4.

For the purpose of the following analyses, we rewrite the MSE budget in eq. 3 as (e.g., Chou and Neelin, 2003):

$$NEI - \left\{ \overline{\vec{u}} \cdot \nabla_h \bar{h} \right\} - \left\{ \overline{\omega} \partial_p \bar{h} \right\} - \nabla_h \cdot \left\{ \overline{h' \vec{u}'} \right\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left\{ \overline{\mathcal{E}} \right\} \quad (6)$$

to expose the separate role of the horizontal and vertical MSE advection (respectively, second and third term on the left-hand side) by the mean flow and the eddy MSE flux divergence (fourth

Figure 27: Panels a) and b): the precipitation climatology of C4-kGMCs for months July, August and September for the first ten years (2020-2029). Panels c) and d): precipitation bias of C4-kGMCs relative to GPCP observations (shown in panel g)). Panels e) and f): near-future precipitation trend of C4-kGMCs for years 2040-2049 relative to years 2020-2029. The area marked by the blue rectangle here represents the Sahel and is used for computing area-averaged vertical profiles of the MSE budget shown in Figure 28. Left panels show ICON4 simulation (ICON4) and right ones show IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation (FIFS4). Panel g) show the GPCP climatology for comparison.

term).

Vertical profiles of the horizontal and vertical MSE advection terms in JAS averaged over the Sahel region denoted by the rectangular box in Figure 27 are shown in Figure 28. In agreement with results of Hill et al. (2017), both models show significant values of horizontal MSE advection (implying import of drier air from the Sahara) below 600 hPa. However, the magnitude of the horizontal advection term is roughly three times larger in FIFS4 than in ICON4, and its influence extends to a deeper layer. While causality is hard to infer, these differences are consistent with the stronger monsoon extending well into the southern Sahara in ICON4. Similarly, the

Figure 28: Vertical profiles for C4-kGCMs of a) the horizontal, b) the vertical MSE advection tendency [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$] and c) the vertical pressure velocity [Pa s^{-1}], averaged over the Sahel region (see blue rectangle in Fig. 27) and months JAS. It is shown both the time averages over the first and last ten years for C4-kGCMs, as well as their difference ($\Delta\text{-CC}$), and also for reference ERA5 reanalyses for the time period 1979-2014. Blue colors are used for ICON ngc4008 simulation (ICON4) and red ones for IFS_9-FESOM_5-production simulation (FIFS4).

projected WAM intensification in ICON4 (see Fig.27e) is accompanied by a weakening of the MSE advection by the Saharan shallow circulation between 900 and 600 hPa. FIFS4 shows instead an opposite trend.

The differing behaviors in ICON4 and FIFS4 in terms of precipitation biases and trends are also consistent with different vertical profiles of vertical pressure velocity (Figure 28c), with FIFS4 and ERA5 featuring bottom-heavy and ICON4 top-heavy upward motions. This is consistent with ICON4 simulating deep convection over the entire domain and FIFS4 more realistically capturing the presence of the shallow meridional overturning circulation, and associated shallower motion, in the poleward extent of the selected domain.

In summary, our analyses confirm that a faithful representation of the Saharan shallow meridional circulation is integral to a realistic representation of the WAM and is implicated in determining its response to warming. While the interactive nature of the coupling between these two circulations does not allow us to assess causality, it provides a fruitful avenue for future investigations.

3.3 West African Monsoon variability, extreme rainfall, and climate change

West Africa experiences a complex and highly variable rainfall regime governed by interactions between large-scale climate drivers and mesoscale processes. A key driver of West African rainfall variability is the African Easterly Wave (AEW) system, particularly the 3–5-day wave modes that modulate convective activity and are linked to the formation of Mesoscale Convective Systems (MCSs) (Fink and Reiner, 2003; Janiga and Thorncroft, 2014). AEWs typically

manifest at 600–700 hPa on either side of the African Easterly Jet (AEJ), play a key role in the high-frequency variability of precipitation associated with the West African Monsoon (WAM) and contribute significantly to the annual rainfall over the Sahel.

Future climate projections of global and regional climate models show contrasting results in AEW activity, with some works suggesting stronger activity and others a weaker one, especially over the southern track (Skinner and Diffenbaugh, 2014; Martin and Thorncroft, 2015; Hannah and Aiyyer, 2017; Brannan and Martin, 2019; Kebe et al., 2020; Bercos-Hickey and Patricola, 2021; Raj et al., 2023). However, traditional CMIP-type climate models struggle to capture AEWs and related rainfall extremes due to their coarse resolution and biases in simulating the regional-scale convective dynamics (Ruti and Dell’Aquila, 2010). While regional climate models (RCMs) have been employed to address some of these limitations, they often rely on boundary conditions from global models, leading to inconsistencies in sea surface temperature (SST) patterns and their influence on AEW dynamics (Sylla et al., 2013).

The NextGEMS simulations offer a unique opportunity to evaluate the impact of climate change on AEW and related precipitation with self-consistent and high-resolution models, which are potentially more capable of simulating the delicate interplay of convection, wind dynamics and topographical features that are key to the initiation and propagation of AEW. Among the different simulations, we focus here on the cycle 4 IFS-FESOM 30-year long simulations. The simulations were run at 9 km resolution for the atmosphere component in the horizontal (tco1279-NG5 grid) and 5 km in the ocean. They consist on a set of twin experiments that differ on the boundary conditions (greenhouse gasses, ozone and aerosols) consistent with an historical period (1990-2019, simulation IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist in table 3) and a projection following SSP3-7.0 scenario (O’Neill et al., 2016) for the 2020-2049 period (simulation IFS_9-FESOM_5-production in table 3).

We begin by assessing the capability of the model to represent AEW by comparing the mean wave characteristics of the IFS historical simulation with those from ERA5 reanalysis. Specifically, we show the standard deviation of 3–5 day bandpass-filtered Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE) in JJAS (Fig29a,b), computed as $EKE = \frac{1}{2}(u'^2 + v'^2)$, where u' and v' represent the 3–5 day bandpass-filtered zonal and meridional wind components. EKE is a measure of sub-synoptic-scale variability, and increased EKE values are often associated with stronger and/or more frequent AEWs. The spatial pattern of EKE shows maximum values located along the West African coast in ERA5. Though the overall pattern of EKE simulated by the IFS is similar, the model consistently underestimates it across the region compared to ERA5. Interestingly, it simultaneously overestimates the variability in precipitation in the 3-5 day band (Fig. 29c,d). However, as was discussed in the previous section, the model reasonably captures the precipitation pattern over West Africa, with a tendency to underestimate the latter over land, except over regions of high orography (Fig. 27c).

This apparent discrepancy between too strong rainfall variability at 3-5 days and reasonable mean precipitation is further analyzed in Fig30a,b, where the differences between mean precipitation falling during days when there is AEW activity (AEW days) is compared to those days in which there was no AEW activity (non-AEW days). To isolate AEW days, a 3–5-day Butterworth bandpass filter was applied to the meridional wind component at 700 hPa at the base point located at 1°W and 11.5°N over the June–September (JJAS) season (as in Raj et al., 2023).

Figure 29: Simulation of AEWs and precipitation variability in JJAS season: EKE (m^2/s^2) in the 3-5 day band at 700 hPa (a, b); rainfall variability in the 3-5 day band (shaded in mm/day). Left column shows the estimate from ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) (a) and MSWEP (Beck et al., 2019) (c), while right column shows the estimates from the IFS historical simulation (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist)

AEW days were identified as those corresponding to wind anomalies exceeding the 90th percentile or falling below the 10th percentile of the filtered distribution. A ± 2 -day temporal offset was applied to account for wave evolution, and duplicate days were excluded to avoid redundancy. The resulting set of unique days was classified as AEW days, while all remaining days within the JJAS season were designated as non-AEW days. Fig30a,b shows that in the observational record, AEW events contribute substantially to rainfall over the Sahel and the Guinean coast, indicating their dominant role in modulating precipitation in these regions. In contrast, the model exhibits a pronounced dipole structure, with enhanced AEW-related rainfall concentrated in a zonally continuous band between 10° – 15° N, encompassing the Sahel. South of this AEW-dominated rainbelt, the equatorial Atlantic displays a secondary rainbelt primarily associated with non-AEW events. Both features are more zonally continuous and intense in the model compared to observations and are statistically significant, suggesting an over-amplification of the AEW signal and its latitudinal separation from non-AEW precipitation within the IFS simulation. In addition, Fig30c,d shows that the over-amplification of the AEW signal in the model is also present in the extreme events of rainfall, which were defined as those rainy days (days above 1 mm of rain) that exceeded the 95th percentile. While the AEW vs non-AEW contrast in the occurrence of moderate rainfall events has no clear structure in the observations, the model also shows a meridional dipole with higher occurrence to the north in AEW days (not shown). In summary, these findings suggest that though the mean seasonal values of rainfall in the model show a pattern consistent with those from observations, the model is biased towards too much convection and rainfall organization related to AEWs. Indeed, when analyzing the AEW energetics, there is an overestimation of the convection-related baroclinic conversion and diabatic generation terms, while most other terms show a very high consistency with those obtained

Figure 30: Simulation of precipitation associated to AEWs in JJAS season: difference in mean rainfall (a, b, in mm/day) and occurrence of extreme rainfall days (c, d, in % of days) during days with AEW activity and days with no AEW activity. Dots mark p values smaller than 0.05 for the local null hypothesis of equal means. Left column shows the estimate from MSWEP (Beck et al., 2019) (a, c), while right column shows the estimates from the IFS historical simulation (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist)

from ERA5 reanalysis (not shown).

Regarding the projected changes in AEW activity, figure 31a reveals a zonal dipole structure in EKE at 700 hPa, with a strong increase over West Africa, suggesting a significant intensification of AEW activity, especially over the northern and southern flanks of the African Easterly Jet (located at around 15°N). This increase is consistent with the enhancement of the number of AEW days from 37 % in the historical simulation to 47% in the projection (the threshold used to detect AEW days was fixed and defined from the historical simulation). In contrast, a large region over the north tropical Atlantic exhibits decreased EKE, with anomalies dropping below $-0.5 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$. This suggests a weakening of AEW activity over the Atlantic, potentially linked to the weakening of Atlantic hurricane activity. This dipole pattern implies a spatial reorganization of AEW activity under future climate conditions, with increased wave amplitude and occurrence frequency over land and reduced activity over the ocean. Over land, the AEW enhancement is consistent with a thermodynamically and dynamically intensification of 3–5-day AEW energetics (not shown). The projected changes in the potential vorticity (PV) provide a potential explanation for such amplification. One of the key dynamical features essential for AEW growth is the reversal of the meridional potential vorticity (PV) gradient, a mechanism that facilitates the necessary barotropic and baroclinic instability for wave amplification (Thorncroft and Blackburn, 1999; Dickinson and Molinari, 2000; Diaz and Aiyyer, 2013). Figure 31b highlights a pronounced

Figure 31: Projected changes in AEW activity and precipitation: Difference between the projection (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production) and the historical (IFS_9-FESOM_5-production-hist) IFS simulations in EKE (m^2/s^2) in the 3-5 day band at 700 hPa (a); potential vorticity ($PV = -g(\partial\theta/\partial p)(\zeta + f)$ where ζ is the relative vorticity, f is the Coriolis parameter, and g is the acceleration due to gravity) at 700 hPa (b); rainfall (mm/day) during days with AEW activity (c) and non-AEW days (d); occurrence of extreme rainfall days (% of days) during days with AEW activity (e) and non-AEW days (f). Dots in panels a through d mark p values smaller than 0.05 for the local null hypothesis of equal means.

increase in the PV inversion band centered around 10°N over eastern Africa (the region where AEW originate). This enhancement of the PV gradient in the projection could play a significant role in supporting the projected increase in both the occurrence frequency and intensity of AEWs. In turn, the main driver of the PV amplification shown over eastern Africa is an increase in static stability (not shown), which is consistent with results from previous studies about warming climate where enhanced upper-tropospheric warming leads to a weakened lapse rate (Knutson and Manabe, 1995). The observed change in static stability contributes to the strengthening of the PV inversion and may partly explain the projected increase in AEW activity.

Regarding projected changes in rainfall, figure 31c,d show an enhancement of mean precipitation over the central Sahel and a drying of the westernmost Sahel, both in AEW and non-AEW days. The change in both sets contribute to the overall west-east dipole pattern in the mean precipitation (not shown), which is consistent with the mean projected changes from coarser grid models (e.g. Monerie et al., 2020; Biasutti, 2013). The effect of the enhancement in the number of AEW days in the projection show a small contribution to the total mean rainfall change pat-

tern (not shown). In addition, figure 31e,f show an enhancement of the occurrence of extreme rainfall events over West Africa, while moderate events (those below the 75th percentile) tend to decrease as well as the total number of days (not shown), suggesting a shift of the rainfall regime over the Sahel towards fewer events but with higher intensity. Interestingly, as this shift is shown in both sets, AEW and non-AEW days, it suggests that the projected enhancement of AEW strength and activity are not the main driver for the rainfall regime shift.

3.4 Interannual variability of African Easterly Waves and related extreme rainfall

Sea surface temperature (SST) variability can modulate the position and strength of the African Easterly Jet (AEJ), which, in turn, provides a guide for African Easterly Waves (AEW), as was explained in the previous section. An example of this modulation is the Atlantic El Niño mode, which, by strengthening the Atlantic inter-tropical convergence zone rainband, enhances African easterly wave activity and low-level cyclonic vorticity across the deep tropical eastern North Atlantic (Kim et al., 2023). In this section we explore the links between SST variability and the AEW activity related with extreme rainfall simulated by cycle 2 ICON 30-year long simulations, previously analysed in section 2.2: experiments *ngc2013* and *rthk001* (table 3), which only vary in their representation of the first 20 meters of the ocean, with 10 layers in *ngc2013* and 2 layer in *rthk001*.

To focus on AEWs related to strong precipitation we use a metric based on cluster analysis, which has been previously applied to identify the circulation patterns affecting rainfall in the region (Moron et al., 2008). We apply k-mean methodology to the the daily 700hPa geopotential height in the North African continent to identify weather regimes driving extreme rainfall over West Africa. The analysis begins by calculating the principal components (PCs) of the extended summer (june to september) daily anomalies of geopotential height at 700 hPa. To calculate such daily anomalies the climatological mean of the associated month is subtracted to the daily value. We choose the 10 first modes to have a complete base for the k-mean algorithm. The algorithm then identifies the number of weather regimes able to distinguish those driving extreme rainfall events in a location around Dakar (Senegal), which is a very populated region. A cost function as in Moron et al. (2008) is calculated in order to distinguish between wet and dry clusters and 4 main clusters are identified. Everyday of the summer season is then associated with a total accumulated rainfall and a cluster.

To identify if one of the clusters characterizes a AEW passing through the region of analysis, a composite analysis is done for the days before and after a particular cluster (Figs. 32 and 33). For each lag, the average of 700hPa geopotential height along the years is calculated and a tracking of the wave is performed. Taking the Hovmöller diagram along time for all the longitudes at a fixed latitude of 15°N, we can identify the propagation of the wave and its characteristics. The Hovmöller diagram is presented together with the frequency of occurrence of that particular cluster. Also, the total accumulated rainfall in Dakar is shown for each cluster. The metric is able to identify AEWs propagating westward with a phase speed of 3 to 5 days, compatible with those identified in the literature (figs. 32 and 33, top panels).

Another important diagnostic is the interannual variability of these weather regimes and its relation with SST variability. To investigate it, the frequency of each cluster for each year is calcu-

NGC2013

Figure 32: TOP PANEL: Hovmöller diagram (longitude-lag) of the propagation of each of the identified meteorological regimes on the 700 hPa geopotential height along the west African coast (at 15N) for the ngc2013 simulation. Lag 0 corresponds to the day when the cluster has its maximum in the analysis region. BOTTOM PANEL: regression map of the anomalous frequency of each of the clusters on the anomalous global SSTs. Dots mark regions where local p values are below 0.05. The total cumulative precipitation per day in each cluster and the mean frequency of occurrence is indicated in the title of each plot.

lated by counting the number of times that a cluster appear in each of the years and along the whole period of study. The resultant index indicates the frequency variability of each weather regime and can be interpreted as a measure of the changes in the AEW wave activity. By regressing the SST seasonal anomalies onto this index we can look for drivers of this variability (figs. 32 and 33, bottom panels). Interannual variability of AEW frequency changes are related to a tropical basin interaction mode. The clusters accumulating more extreme rainfall are related to years in which the Pacific Ocean presents La Niña conditions and the equatorial Atlantic El Niño conditions (cluster 3 in 33 and clusters 2 and 4 in 32), in agreement with recent studies (Kim et al., 2023; Bercos-Hickey and Patricola, 2024). By construction, the opposite takes place for a decrease in the AEWs frequency.

Interestingly, strong differences appear between the simulation with high vertical resolution in the upper part of the ocean (ngc2013) and that with lower vertical resolution (rthk001), in such

rTHK001

Figure 33: Same as fig. 32 but for the rthk001 simulation.

a way that the propagation of waves in the former present more clear propagating atmospheric structures in clusters 2 and 3 than any other structure in the rthk001 experiment. As was explained in section 2.2, the rthk001 experiment tends to simulate higher SST tropical variability, which is also suggested when comparing fig. 33 to 32. However, in the rthk001 simulation the propagation of the atmospheric anomalies does not reach regions as far away in the western Atlantic when compared to ngc2013. As the propagating AEW have been shown to act as seeds of tropical cyclones, this suggests a potential different impact on tropical cyclones and their propagation in these two simulations, an aspect that would be interesting to analyze in the future.

3.5 Southeast Asian climate and weather extremes

Kilometer-scale ESMs could be beneficial to improve the simulation of climate and weather systems in marginal seas due to their capacity to resolve these orographic complex regions. One such area is located in Southeast Asia, between the tropical Pacific warm pool and the warmer side of Indian Ocean, and constitutes one of the most convective tropical regions (Teo et al., 2011). One type of extreme weather event in this region is monsoon cold surges (abrupt intensification of northeasterly monsoon winds over the South China Sea), activating cumulus convection and precipitation (e.g. Koseki et al., 2014; Koseki et al., 2023) and inducing natural

disaster like flooding (e.g. Tangan et al., 2008). Here, we assess how nextGEMS ESMs (cycle 2 ICON simulations ngc2013 and rthk001 in table 3, Segura et al., 2025) and AWI-CM3-HR (IFS-FESOM, see table 3), Sein et al., 2025 tbs) can reproduce the properties of monsoon cold surges and corresponding rainfall comparing with ERA5 and some CMIP6 ESMs (MIROC6; Tatebe et al., 2019, TaiESM1; Wang et al., 2021, and MRI-ESM2-0; Yukimoto et al., 2019).

Figure 34: Wind rose plots of daily cold surge index (winds at 850hPa averaged in the blue box of the geographical map) for ERA5, nextGEMS models and CMIP6 models in December.

We estimate the a cold surge (CS) Index and top-3 wind regime of direction in December from the daily wind field at 850 hPa (Fig.34). The top-3 wind regime of ERA5 concentrates between 200° and 220° of direction and dominates by more than 56 percent of the total data. Moreover, strong surge (defined as those events with wind speed larger than the mean of wind speed in the 3 wind regimes plus one standard deviation) within the top-3 wind regime has 9 percent of the total data (Fig.34a). The ICON simulations capture well this characteristic of the wind regime and strong surge even though the westward wind regime is relatively more dominant than in ERA5 (Fig.34b,c, and d). Among the nextGEMS ESMs, AWI-CM3-HR overperforms other models in terms of monsoon wind regime as in Fig.34d (note that there is only 10-years data available for AWI-CM3-HR). Contrastingly, the top-3 wind regime of MIROC6 is biased in southward direction and the dominance of the top-3 wind regime is relatively small (Fig.34e). Additionally, the intensity of daily CS Index is larger than ERA5 and other ESMs. The wind regime of TaiESM1, on the other hand, is biased in too westward direction even though the intensity of winter monsoon is as strong as that of ERA5 (Fig.34f). Among the CMIP6 ESMs, MRI-ESM2-0 is the best one to reproduce the characteristics of short-term variability in winter monsoon circulation (Fig.34g).

The cold surge enhances the rainfall over the South China Sea (Fig.35, Koseki et al., 2014; Koseki et al., 2023). Particularly, along the eastern coast of the Malay Peninsula and to the north of the Borneo Island, the precipitation is reinforced, while rainfall is suppressed above 12°N (Fig.35a). In addition, the rainfall over the Java Sea is also moderately increased due to

Figure 35: Composite anomalies of precipitations (mm/day) in the strong surge of top-3 wind regimes for ERA5, nextGEMS models and CMIP6 models.

the cold surges (Hattori et al., 2011). While the ICON simulations overestimate the response of rainfall to the cold surges over the South China Sea, its qualitative distribution is well captured: intensification to the north of Borneo and the eastern coast of the Malay Peninsula (Figs. 35b and c). In addition, the moderate reinforcement over the Java Sea is realistically generated corresponding to the strong easterly winds. The rainfall response in AWI-CM3-HR is better than the ICON models: the distribution and intensity of wet anomalies over the South China Sea is quite similar to those in ERA5 (Fig. 35d). Especially, the vigorous precipitation over the Malay Peninsula is anchored around the coastal region while the ICON models have a more inland intensification of rainfall (Figs. 35b, c, and d). In the Southern Hemisphere, the rainfall increases successfully over the Java Sea, however a dry anomaly is overestimated in the eastern Sumatra, which can be detected in the ICON models as well (Figs. 35b,c, and d). The wet extremes associated with the cold surges in MIROC6 are extensively overestimated to the north of Borneo (Fig. 35e). Contrastingly, the rainfall over the Malay Peninsula is not reinforced as strongly as ERA5 and the nextGEMS models. This can be because the strong surges in the top-3 wind regimes are biased southward in MIROC6 and therefore, convection and rainfall are activated in more meridional direction as a southward elongated intensification is seen between Sumatra and Borneo. However, the increase in the Southern Hemisphere is well captured in MIROC6. TaiESM1, on the other hand, reproduces westward-shifted wet anomaly over the South China Sea (Fig. 35f). Even though the amount of anomalous rainfall approximately identical with that of TRMM, the core of the intense rainfall over the South China Sea locates over the cold tongue. According to Koseki et al. (2023), the strengthening of precipitation by cold surges does not occur over, but around the cold tongue. The westward-biased monsoon surges tend to activate

convection over the cold SST in TaiESM1. Such biased monsoon surge also leads to failure of increase in the rainfall over the Java Sea (Fig. 35f). In MRI-ESM2, which reproduces the better strong surges, an intensified rainfall pattern is found along the Malay Peninsula and the north of Borneo more realistically than other CMIP6 models while it shifts slightly southward and more moderate than ERA5 (Fig. 35g). The rainfall over the Java Sea is enhanced, but its amplitude is smaller than ERA5 and nextGEMS ESMs.

All in all, this analysis shows that NextGEMS models, by better resolving complex orographical features, provide an improved representation of climate and weather systems over the marginal sea area of Southeast Asia with respect to the one simulated by models with coarser horizontal grids.

3.6 Teleconnections between Atlantic Niño and the Indian Summer Monsoon

The Indian summer monsoon (ISM), occurring during boreal summer, is one of the most prominent features of the global atmospheric circulation. Accounting for the majority of India's annual rainfall, the ISM far surpasses the country's smaller winter rainfall peak in both magnitude and significance. Its impacts extend beyond India, influencing global weather and climate patterns. Given its importance for agriculture, water resources, and economic planning, understanding the drivers and variability of June–September (JJAS) rainfall over India is of critical scientific and societal interest.

The ISM is a fully coupled land–atmosphere–ocean system shaped by both local air–sea interactions and remote climatic drivers. Among others, the Atlantic Niño, which typically peaks during boreal summer like the ISM, has been identified as an important influence. As was explained in previous sections, the Atlantic Niño is characterized by SST anomalies in the cold tongue region of the eastern tropical Atlantic and along the southwestern African coast (e.g. Fig. 10). Through local air–sea interactions, tropical Atlantic SST anomalies influence the position and strength of the Atlantic intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ), driving atmospheric circulation patterns that can extend far beyond the Atlantic basin (e.g. Fig. 5).

Previous research has highlighted the role of the eastern equatorial Atlantic SST in modulating ISM rainfall via atmospheric teleconnections, particularly through Eurasian Rossby wave trains acting as an atmospheric bridge (Barimalala et al., 2012; Kucharski et al., 2009). More recent work (Sahoo and Yadav, 2021; Yadav, 2017; Yadav et al., 2018; Yadav et al., 2020; Yadav, 2021) has detailed how the Atlantic Niño influences in particular northwest and north-central India by exciting a stationary Rossby wave that modulates the Tibetan High and strengthens convective activity over the subcontinent during the monsoon season.

The teleconnections between the Atlantic Niño and the ISM represent a complex, coupled system involving interactions between the land, atmosphere, and ocean across vast spatial scales. Until now, these interactions have been studied primarily using observational datasets and reanalysis products. Comprehensive, global, high-resolution models, such as the NextGEMS simulations, now offer new opportunities to explore the linkage between tropical Atlantic SST anomalies to remote climate responses, including impacts on the Indian monsoon. In this study, we analyze the 30-year long IFS_9-FESOM_5-production scenario run (2020–2049, see table

3), conducted in cycle 4 under the SSP3-7.0 forcing scenario, to investigate the teleconnections between the Atlantic Niño and ISM. This simulation, with an atmospheric resolution of 9 km and an ocean resolution of 5 km, provides a novel framework to gain new insights into the mechanisms and variability underlying the Atlantic SST–ISM connection.

First, we calculated the Atlantic Niño Index (ANI) for the simulation output. The ANI is defined as SST anomalies averaged over the cold tongue region between 3°S – 3°N , 20°W – 0° . Further, we detrended the resulting time series. Atlantic Niño/Niña events are defined as SST anomalies above/below the threshold of $0.5^{\circ}\text{C}/-0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a duration of 90 consecutive days (Fig. 36). This results in 6 Atlantic Niño events during the simulation period of which 4 occur during boreal summer and 4 Atlantic Niña events, which all occur during boreal summer.

Figure 36: Detrended simulated SST anomalies in the Atlantic Cold Tongue region (3°S – 3°N , 20°W – 0°W) in the IFS_9-FESOM_5-production experiment. The red and blue dotted lines indicate the temperature threshold for Atlantic Niño/Atlantic Niña events, respectively. Shaded areas highlight the identified Atlantic Niño (red) and Atlantic Niña (blue) events.

Next, we conducted a grid point wise correlation analysis based on monthly averaged detrended precipitation and the ANI. The resulting correlation coefficients are shown in Figure 37. As expected, correlation is highest in the tropical Atlantic, directly related to the local SST anomalies. Moderate positive correlation of $r = 0.3$ can be found in central north India while moderate negative correlation of $r = -0.3$ along the west coast of India, adjacent the Bay of Bengal. The latter is in agreement with previous studies based on the observational record by Sahoo and Yadav (2021) and Yadav and Roxy (2019) while the correlation in central north India is of the opposite sign than reported by Sahoo and Yadav (2021) and Yadav and Roxy (2019). However, it should be noted here that they calculated correlation between ANI and precipitation based only on the ISM months June to September, while we include the whole time series which might lead to a reduced correlation.

To further analyze the impact of ANI on the ISM we calculated composites of precipitation during the ISM season June to September (JJAS) for years during which an Atlantic Niño or Atlantic

Figure 37: Correlation coefficient between the monthly detrended global precipitation and ANI in the IFS_9-FESOM_5-production experiment. Black dots indicate the 95% significance level.

Niña occurred compared to years where neither of the events occurred. For this analysis we only included Atlantic Niño events that occurred during boreal summer as Atlantic Niño events outside this season are not expected to effect ISM rainfall or if so, differently. The resulting precipitation composites are shown in Figure 38. Figure 38a - c show the mean precipitation for each of the event types while Figure 38d and e visualize the differences of Atlantic Niño and Niña years compared to event free years.

The composite analysis reveals a clear impact of ANI on ISM. Independent of the occurrence of an Atlantic Niño or Niña event, the precipitation is strongest along the Bay of Bengal, the northeast India region, along the Himalaya and along the coast of Bangladesh and Myanmar, which is the expected rainfall pattern for the ISM season. However, in comparison, during the occurrence of an Atlantic Niño, precipitation is significantly reduced by 5 to 15 mm/day along the Indian coast as well as in Bangladesh in Myanmar while the area centered around 25°N/80°E experiences an increase in precipitation of up to 10 mm/day. This area coincides which the usual location of the Tibetan High. This corroborates the results by Sahoo and Yadav (2021) who find that the Atlantic Niño leads to an intensification of the Tibetan High during Atlantic Niño driven by atmospheric Rossby waves, which causes an amplification of upper tropospheric divergence, which, in turn, can then reinforce updraft motion at the lower-troposphere and lead to increased the convective activity and precipitation. However, in their study the core of the Tibetan high is shifted further to the northwest, leading to increased precipitation in northeast India, rather than the central part. We do find an increase of 200hPa geopotential height during Atlantic Niño years, indicating a strengthening of the Tibetan high in the region of increased precipitation during Atlantic Niño years in IFS-FESOM (Fig. 39).

However, we did find the pattern of geopotential height anomalies connecting the tropical Atlantic and India as described in Sahoo and Yadav (2021).

Figure 38: Composite mean JJAS precipitation in mm/day for years with Atlantic Niño occurrence (a), Atlantic Niña occurrence (b) and years without any event (c) in the IFS_9-FESOM_5-production experiment. The differences between Atlantic Niño or Niña event years and years without any event are shown in d) and e), respectively. Here, black dots indicate that the differences are within the 95% significance level following t-test significance testing.

The impact of Atlantic Niña events, i.e. cold SST anomalies, is opposite to Atlantic Niño events. However, despite the SST amplitude of Atlantic Niña events being of comparable magnitude to Atlantic Niño events, their effect on ISM precipitation is weaker. That is, Atlantic Niña events coincide with a slight precipitation increase along the Bay of Bengal as well as Bangladesh and Myanmar and a slight decrease in central India.

In summary, this study analyzed the teleconnections between the Atlantic Niño and the ISM using a 30-year high-resolution IFS-FESOM simulation under the SSP3-7.0 scenario. Correlation and composite analyses revealed that Atlantic Niño events lead to reduced precipitation along India's coast, Bangladesh, and Myanmar, but increased rainfall over central India, linked to a strengthening of the Tibetan High. In contrast, Atlantic Niña events showed weaker and more limited effects on ISM rainfall.

While our results confirm the significant role of Atlantic SST anomalies in modulating ISM variability, the underlying physical mechanisms — particularly the nature of the atmospheric bridges driving these teleconnections — still remain an open question. Further research is needed to clarify these mechanisms and to investigate why some affected regions in our study differ from those highlighted in previous work.

Figure 39: Composites of simulated 200 hPa geopotential height for Atlantic Niño years (a), Atlantic Niña years (b) and years without an event (c). Black lines denote the 12660 and 12675 m isoline to illustrate the core of the Tibetan high.

4 Conclusion

Being the main source of interannual variability, much effort has been devoted to evaluate the representation of ENSO and its teleconnections. Overall, the spatial pattern of SST anomalies in the ENSO region, as well as across the global domain, exhibit a strong resemblance between the IFS model and observations. However, the amplitude of variability in the Niño 3.4 region is too strong, providing associated SST patterns away from the tropical Pacific too weak when measured with respect to the Niño 3.4 anomaly. The ENSO associated precipitation and circulation patterns simulated by the model resemble the observed ones, though magnitudes tend to be too weak, especially for the Aleutian Low, which the model projects to weaken even further by the mid 21st century. While 30-year periods are typically sufficient to capture the general characteristics of ENSO, the fact that the two simulations represent successive periods somewhat limits our ability to robustly detect or attribute changes in ENSO behaviour or teleconnections under climate change. Nonetheless, the clear differences seen in some teleconnection patterns—such as the Aleutian low—offer an initial indication of how these connections might evolve in a warming climate. Away from the Pacific basin, the model is also capable of simulating an Atlantic El Niño, though with too strong interannual variability and Atlantic-Pacific connection. While ENSO’s variability in the climate change projection remains the same, the Atlantic El Niño variability shows a clear enhancement, which is not consistent with CMIP-type of model response. The ICON model also shows too strong variability in the Atlantic region with a strong warm bias, while biases in the mean and variability are not as strong in the Pacific region.

The NextGEMS models are also capable of realistically representing other features as the synoptic-scale flow in the subtropical regions with stratocumulus-topped boundary layer regimes, as well as the vertical structure with shallow clouds below 3 km height. However, they present differences in the height of the base and the cloud liquid content related to subgrid mixing representation and other environmental factors. One aspect that remains to be ascertained is the sensitivity to the vertical grid spacing, as nextGEMS experiments focused on varying horizontal grid spacing. To some extent, this question has been addressed by varying the stability function in the Smagorinsky turbulence scheme. The strong effect of this part of the parametrization in the results warrants further study in this direction, possibly varying vertical grid spacing.

Another feature requiring even higher horizontal resolution are the coastal trapped waves in the tropical Angolan upwelling system, which the IFS models is capable of properly representing. However, SSTs in the region are still being overestimated and the model projects a strong warming there.

A particular pervasive bias in NextGEMS simulations are mean precipitation averages in the tropics. Both symmetrical (too much tropical mean rainfall) and antisymmetrical (too little difference between the NH and the SH rainfall) biases are unmitigated in the last cycle of simulations. These biases are, in turn, related to the models being too symmetric across the Equator in key energetic terms such as the TOA radiation (in IFS) and the surface radiation (in ICON).

The NextGEMS multi-decadal simulations allow the detailed investigation of air-sea coupling processes in regions as the tropical Pacific for different conditions by picking case studies of El Niño or La Niña conditions. These analyses show that during El Niño, westerly wind events are more frequent, while strong easterlies can still align with warm SST anomalies due to reduced cloud cover and increased solar input. Moreover, NextGEMS 30-yr long simulations allow the exploration of how modes of SST variability and tropical basin interactions can change following a modification in the background climate. The twin ICON simulations performed in cycle 2 were analysed to show that by reducing the resolution in the top 20-m top layer the westerly wind bias in the equatorial Atlantic is reduced providing a stronger Bjerknes feedback and a more intense Atlantic El Niño pattern. It is possible that the bias reduction is due to compensating errors. However, the analysis shows that the stronger variability in the low vertical resolution run leads, in turn, to a stronger connection with the Pacific basin. The simulated ENSO variability also changes providing a stronger link to the Atlantic impacting the coastal upwelling regions in that basin.

Another line of research pursued in WP7 and detailed in this deliverable has been the evaluation of climate and its variability in monsoon regions, with a special focus on the West African Monsoon. Application of the energetic framework shows that the misrepresentation of tropical rainfall by the ICON model cannot be solely explained as due to meridional shifts of the ITCZ. The precipitation bias patterns shows a zonal complex structure tied to the misrepresentation of the atmospheric energy divergent transports which, in turn, seem mostly led by biases in the latent heat fluxes at the surface, suggesting errors over land as potential strong contributors. The energetic framework also helps explain the difference in the representation of monsoons by NextGEMS models. In particular, ICON is biased towards a too wet West African monsoon, while IFS seems to show dry biases but of smaller amplitude. These difference are consistent with a different circulation, with ICON model mainly exporting moist static energy through the divergent circulation with a very strong deep convection, while IFS model exports it through the horizontal advection, mainly tied to the shallow meridional overturning circulation located over the Saharan low, which tends to hinder the northward extension of the monsoon, providing a representation closer to the observed one.

Analyses of processes related to the monsoons have also provided interesting findings. For instance, a closer inspection of IFS production simulations in cycle 4 shows that even though biases in the mean rainfall are weak for the West African Monsoon, the model is overrepresenting the effect of organized convection linked to the passage of African Easterly Waves (AEW), which can be traced to the baroclinic conversion and diabatic generation terms for these waves.

This overrepresentation also affects the occurrence of extremes of rainfall, which is too strongly linked to the passage of AEW in the model. The comparison of the IFS projection and historical simulations in cycle 4 suggests AEW will be more frequent and stronger in the near future over land, where mean rainfall and extreme rainfall events are also expected to increase. In addition to climate change, we show that other changes in the background climate and of the interannual teleconnections can lead to strong changes in the frequency and patterns of these types of waves. Analysis of cycle 2 ICON runs show that this model is also capable of simulating easterly waves over West Africa during summer, which are related to strong precipitation. However, using a metric based on cluster analysis we show that their propagation into the Atlantic is hindered in the simulation with strong interannual variability, potentially impacting the development of tropical cyclones.

The enhanced horizontal resolution of NextGEMS models allows them to better capture other monsoonal regimes. This is particularly evident in orographic complex areas as the marginal sea region in Southeast Asia, where kilometer-scale models outperform coarser ones in the representation of daily wind regimes and, especially strong cold surges and their associated rainfall. However, the NextGEMS models still present biases there, like too much inland rainfall in ICON and a too dry eastern Sumatra in IFS.

In addition to a better representation of monsoon mean climate, NextGEMS models can be useful to better understand drivers of interannual variability of monsoon regimes. In particular, the analysis performed with the IFS model shows it is capable of representing the connection at interannual time scales of the Indian monsoon and the Atlantic Niño, through the intensification of the Tibetan High during Atlantic Niño years.

All in all, NextGEMS simulations are capable of simulating climate and its variability for a wide range of tropical phenomena, including air-sea coupled modes such as the Pacific or the Atlantic Niños and their interactions, and monsoon regimes and their synoptic and interannual variability. This allows us to use them to improve our understanding of processes in the climate system and to explore scientific questions, like those related to the expected changes in the climate system and the role of the background state in shaping teleconnections. Even though NextGEMS models present a great step forward in our capability to simulate the climate system, biases still remain. The models still show too strong tropical rainfall, which is too symmetrical across the equator, with complex zonal shifts tied to the misrepresentation of atmospheric energetic transports. Warm biases over the tropical eastern Atlantic are also still present in NextGEMS models. Furthermore, results in this deliverable suggest that absence of mean biases cannot guarantee processes are not misrepresented by a model, as is the case of IFS over West Africa, suggesting process-based evaluation is needed.

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